

dissociation of phenolic OH and pK_2 corresponding to the association of proton to azomethine nitrogen were determined at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values were also computed for metal-ligand systems and from \bar{n} vs pL curves (Fig. 2) $\log K_1$ values for various metal complexes were determined by half integral method. All the values were further corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ vs pL . The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-N-diethylaminoaniline.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-N-diethylaminoaniline.

TABLE 1

	$t=30^\circ$			$\mu=0.1 M$			
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	9.28	12.23	12.55	7.56	7.96	7.75	9.33
$\log K_2$	6.75	—	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Pr^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Sm^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Nd^{3+}$.

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The authors record their thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay for valuable suggestions.

References

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Studies on Potentiometric Stability of Some Trivalent Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-(4''-Morpholinyl)Aniline

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IN the present communication, complexation equilibria of metal complexes of Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-(4''-morpholinyl)aniline have been studied potentiometrically. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and formation constants ($\log K_1$) of its metal chelates have been determined following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing alcoholic solution of equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 202° (observed). The purity of the compound was tested by tlc and elemental analysis. (Found: C, 75.80; H, 6.10; N, 8.26. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{20}N_2O_2$; C, 75.90; H, 6.02, N, 8.13%.)

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid of A.R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details are the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants were calculated from the titration data by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹. The \bar{n}_A values at various B values (pH meter readings) were determined and from the plot of \bar{n}_A vs B (Fig. 1) the pK_1 corresponding

to the dissociation of phenolic OH and pK_2 corresponding to the association of proton to azomethine nitrogen were determined at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values were also computed for metal-ligand systems and from \bar{n} vs pL curves, (Fig. 2) $\log K_1$ values for various metal complexes were determined by half integral method. All the values

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-(4''-morpholinyl)aniline.

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were further corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log (\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ vs pL . The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1							
	$t=30^\circ$				$\mu=0.1 M$		
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	10.34	8.06	8.25	8.02	7.48	7.52	7.72
$\log K_2$	4.35	—	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Pr^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Sm^{3+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay for valuable suggestions.

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Viscosity of Glycine in Alcohol-Water Mixtures at 308.15 K

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VISCOSITY and volumetric studies have been reported on amino acids in aqueous solutions¹⁻⁴. These measurements can be all the more interesting if made in mixed solvents containing water. The viscosity and volumetric studies of amino acids in solvents other than water do not appear to have been made except in water + dimethyl formamide⁵. There has been considerable interest in aqueous solutions of the lower aliphatic alcohols because of their unique structural relationship to pure water⁶. The viscosities and densities of glycine in alcohol + water mixtures containing up to 25% (w/w) of alcohol have, therefore, been measured over a range of concentrations at 308.15 K. The alcohols studied are methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol and *t*-butanol. The data are used to calculate the viscosity B- and D- coefficients.

Experimental

Methods of purification of methanol (BDH, AR), ethanol (Bengal Chemical), *n*-propanol (Riedel, AR) and *t*-butanol (S. Merck, LR) were the same as described by Vogel⁷. Purified liquids were stored in well stoppered bottles and were distilled afresh before use. Glycine (extra pure grade) was obtained from E. Merck and was used without further purification except drying in an oven at 403 K for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was stored over anhydrous calcium oxide in a vacuum desiccator.

Solutions were prepared on molar basis in double distilled water and vacuum corrections were applied to all weighings.

Ubbelohde type⁸ capillary viscometer was used for viscosity measurements. The accuracy in time

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